

Privacy issues for Institutional and Learning analytics to measure Digital Readiness

Checklist for HEIs

Lawful basis and transparency
Include data related to the measurement of digital readiness (DR) in the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).
Check that the personal data collected to compute DR indicators can be justified by "legitimate interest". When possible, ask users for their explicit consent to collect this data. Carry out a DPIA for each kind of data.
Inform the users about the data collected to compute Digital Readiness indicators. Use the DigiReady+ framework to explain how the data is processed, who has access to it, and how you are keeping it safe. This information should be included in your privacy policy and provided to data subjects at the time you collect the data.
Data security
Protect the data used to measure digital readiness
Encrypt, pseudonymize or anonymize personal data used to measure digital readiness wherever possible.
Create an internal security policy for your team members and build awareness of data protection when employing personal data to measure digital readiness
Conduct a data protection impact assessment if needed and have a process in place to carry it out
Have a process in place to notify the authorities and your data subjects in the event of a data breach
Accountability and governance
Ensure that there is someone responsible for ensuring GDPR compliance across your organization
In case the DigiReady+ consortium or an external party is processing personal data, sign a Data Processing Agreement between your HEI and the external processor.
In case DigiReady+ tools are used by an organization outside the EU, it should appoint a representative with one of the EU member states.
Ensure the DPO is aware of the procedures related to measurement of Digital Readiness.
Privacy rights
It is easy for your users to get access to the information you have about them related to measurement of Digital Readiness
It is easy for your users to make comments or corrections to the data collected to measure Digital Readiness
It is easy for your users to request that their personal data related to Digital Readiness is deleted
When the DigiReady+ tool manages personal data, the user can ask for them and the Digital Readiness should be able to send it to the person
It is easy for your users to object to you processing their data to measure DR